

TESTING THE ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF WILD TURMERIC LEAVES ETHANOL EXTRACT (*Elettariopsis slahmong*) AGAINST *Staphylococcus aureus* AND *Escherichia coli* IN-VITRO

Avelia Firozka (2110422014) – Microbiology Research Laboratory, Biology Department, FMIPA, Andalas University

Wild ginger *Elettariopsis slahmong* C.K. Lim, is a wild plant of the family Zingiberaceae which was first discovered in Thailand by CK Lim this plant, it has a very strong pungent odor called the smelly leavis or stink bug plant (Picheansoonth and Yupparach, 2007). Wild ginger contains essential oils from leaves, rhizomes and roots obtained by hydrodistillation (Magdaulih and Nasir, 2014). Essential oils and volatile compounds from this plant are insecticidal against the *Drosophila melanogaster* insect which is a vector of blood diseases in banana plants (Nasir et al., 2014). Essential oil is the major chemical constituent of all parts of the *Elettariopsis* species. Terpenes, particularly monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes, are the major constituents of this essential oil. It is volatile at temperature room, hence the name volatile oil or ethereal oil. *E. slahmong* is the most volatile amongst the species of *Elettariopsis*. The scent of particularly crushed leaves of *E. slahmong* has a strongly aromatic herb with the distinctive odor of the “stink bug” (Picheansoonthon dan Yupparach, 2007). The stink bug odor of *E. slahmong* probably be attributed to (E)-2- octenal and (E)-2-decenal as it was also detected by Nasir et al (2016) and Nasir (2016). The difference in scence reflects the difference in volatile chemical compositions, mainly monoterpenoids and sesquiterpenoids. Although research has been carried out to test the antibacterial activity of fresh plant extract and etabol, not much research has yet been done to test antibacteric activity of *Elettariopsis slahmong* plants. Specifically, the antibacterial activity of wild turmeric leaf ethanol extract (*Elettariopsis slahmong*) against test bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* has not been tested. Looking at some studies that have been conducted to test the essential oil of *Elettariopsis slahmong*, given that this plant is a wild plant, then there is a huge potential of essential oils in inhibiting the growth of bacteria and pathogens. Plants that have economic value to control pests and diseases. The aim of this study is to determine the antibacterial effects of wild ginger leaves (*Ellettariopsis slahmong*) in vitro.

Research results show that the species of the Zingiberaceae family has the potential to be developed for a variety of purposes. Plants of this family include nutface plasma used in everyday life, such as medicinal plants, spices, as well as the production of essential oils and dyes in industry. (Syamsuardi et al., 2010). Previous research suggests that some species of the Zingiberaceae family may have antibacterial and antifungal properties. For example, Agustin et al., (2021) that *Zingiber macradenium* has antibacterial potential and is used in the treatment of various diseases. In addition, *Cymbopogon nardus* is also potentially a biofungicide to control fungi, as is *Elettariopsis slahmong* which has an effective antifungal activity against *Sclerotium rolfsii*. Furthermore, according to Nasir (2017), this species is also potentially as a biopesticide against disease of cocoa plants. In other studies, n-hexane extract from the *Alpinia aureus* frog also showed significant antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Therefore, this study is to look at the antibacterial capabilities of ethanol extracts of wild turmeric leaves (*Elettariopsis slahmong*) against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* in vitro and how this extract plays a role as an effective antimicrobial agent to inhibit the growth of viruses. In a study Magdaulih et al., (2014) obtained results that the contents of secondary metabolites in *Elettariopsis slahmong* extract have no biocidal effect on the mushroom *Colletotrichum* sp. Nasir (2013) also found that the geraniol content in the leaves and spurs of *Elettariopsis Slahmung* is relatively similar. As a result, *E. slahmong* became ineffective as a fungus control agent. Some studies have shown that only essential oils rich in citronella are effective as antifungal agents. The anti-fungal effects of essential oil components such as citral, geraniol, nerol,

citronellal, fenchone, and linalool have also been tested against *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, and *Fusarium*. Research results show that citronellal has the highest antifungal activity among other ingredients (Aoudou et al., 2009).

Bacteria are microorganisms that cannot be seen with the naked eye and can be seen only with the help of a microscope. (Ramadhani et al., 2018). Pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* are more dangerous and cause both sporadic and endemic infections. (Djide dan Sartini, 2008). To combat and treat pathogenic bacteria in already infected living creatures can be treated with the use of antibiotics. Antibiotic use can cause resistance if not used as intended. (Jawetz, 2005). In this study, we used ethanol extraction techniques. Because ethanol extraction technology is more stable than fresh extracts, it has better quality and quantity of compounds, and can increase the concentration of active ingredients contained in plants as well as enhance the inhibitory effect against microorganisms. (Subrianti et al., 2022). Plant extracts can be used as biofungicides. One of the important compounds found in plant extracts is essential oils. Most essential oils from various plants have antibacterial and antifungal effects (Picheansoonthon dan Yupparach, 2007; Nurmansyah, 2014).

In this study, the antibacterial activity of wild turmeric leaf ethanol extract (*Elettariopsis slahmong*) against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* was tested in vitro using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method (Moghadamtousi et al., 2014). The results of this study aim to show that the ethanol extract of wild turmeric leaves (*Elettariopsis slahmong*) has antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* in vitro. The antibacterial activity of ethanol extracted from wild turmeric leaves has been compared to standard antibiotics in the treatment of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* infections (Ekor, 2014). The mechanisms of action of antimicrobial compounds are generally based on damage to cell walls, changes in membrane permeability, inhibition of protein synthesis, and inhibitions of enzyme work (Pelczar and Chan, 2008). Compounds involved in cell wall damage include phenols, flavonoids, and alkaloids. These phytochemicals can act as natural antibacterials against pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* (Sangeetha dan Asokan, 2015). Previous research has tested the antibacterial activity of the *Elettariopsis slahmong* extract against the test bacteria, but the results indicate that the extract's antibacteric activity is low. It's because of the low content of curcumin. Curcumin is the main active component of turmeric and has an antibacterial activity of 0.2–0.5% (Akrayi dan Kheder, 2013). Test bacterial antibacterial resistance is affected by different treatments at different concentrations, and the difference in incubation time is also one of the factors (Septiani et al., 2017). This is in line with Lovista's (2010) statement that the higher the concentration of *C. vulgaris* extract, the greater its inhibitory effect on pathogenic bacteria.

Elettariopsis slahmong is a wild plant commonly used by the local community as a traditional medicine and a culinary spice. However, its use as an antimicrobial agent, especially antibacterial, is still very low. *E. slahmong* has previously been proven powerful as an insecticide to fight plant diseases. In addition, each plant also showed different antibacterial activity against the tested bacteria. The study aims to identify the potential of ethanol extracted from wild turmeric leaves as an effective antibacterial agent to inhibit the growth of pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. Therefore, this research contributes to the knowledge of the antibacterial potential of wild crops and becomes the basic ingredient for the development of effective and safe traditional medicine.

DAFTAR PUSTAKA

- Agustin, L., Nurainas, Syamsuardi, A., Agustien and Chairul. 2021. *Zingiber macradenium* K. SCHUM, an Endemic Ginger from Sumatera: Traditional Use and Antimicrobe Potential. *Eduvest – Journal of Universal Studies*. 1(10): 1036 – 1046.
- Akrayi, H., F., S., and Kheder, A., K. 2013. Antibacterial Potency of Some Medicinal Plant Extracts on Inhibiting Antibiotic Resistance Property of *Escherichia coli*. *Middle East Journal of Internal Medicine*. 6(4).
- Aoudou, Y., Leopold, T., N., Michel, J., D., P., Xavier, E., F., Moses, M., C. 2009. Antifungal Properties of Essential Oils and Some Constituents to Reduce Foodborne Pathogen. *Journal of Yeast and Fungal Research*. 1(1): 001-008.
- Djide dan Sartini. 2008. *Dasar-Dasar Mikrobiologi Farmasi*. Lepas, Makasar.
- Ekor, V. 2014. Herbal Remedies for Persistent Bacterial Infections: A Review of Potential Phytochemicals. *Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*. 20(8): 647-656.
- Jawetz, Melnick Adelberg's, 2005. *Mikrobiologi Kedokteran*. Edisi 23. Terjemahan oleh Huriwati Hartono. Jakarta: EGC.
- Lovista, V., F. 2010. Pengaruh Konsentrasi Ekstrak *Chlorella vulgaris* terhadap Zona Hambat Bakteri Patogen. *Skripsi*. Fakultas Perikanan dan Ilmu Kelautan. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro.
- Magdaulih, E., and Nasir, N. 2014. Antifungal Activity of Essential Oil of *Cymbopogon nardus* L. and *Elettariopsis slahmong* Lim. Against *Colletotrichum* sp. on Red Dragon Fruit (*Hylocereus polyrhizus*). *Journal Biology UA*. 3(2): 97–102.
- Moghadamtousi, S., Z., Kadir, H., A., Hassandarvish, P., Abubakar, S., and Zandi, K. 2014. A Review on Antibacterial, Antiviral, and Antifungal Activity of Curcumin. *International Journal of Molecular Medicine*. 43(3): 649-654.
- Nasir, N. 2013. **Serangan Penyakit Penting pada Buah Naga *Hylocereus polyrhizus* di Kepulauan Riau. Laporan Penelitian. Jurusan Biologi FMIPA Universitas Andalas. 5 hal.**
- Nasir, N. 2016. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 7(6): 2164-2171.
- Nasir. 2017. Essential Oils from *Elettariopsis slahmong* C. K. Lim and *Cinnamomum burmannii* [Nees & T. Nees] Bl. Inhibit the Colony Growth of *Phytophthora palmivora* of Cocoa. *Scholars Research Library der Pharmacia Lettre*. 9(4): 95–107.
- Nasir, N., Dharma, A., Efdi, M., and Yuhendra, E., F. 2014. Natural Product of Wild Zingiberaceae *Elettariopsis slahmong* Biopesticide to Control the Vector of Banana Blood Disease Bacterium in West Sumatera. *Research of Pharmaceutical Biological and Chemical Science*. 5(5): 1250–1256.
- Nasir N, and Nurmansyah. 2016. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 7(5): 2463-2471.

- Nurmansyah. 2014. Kajian Potensi Minyak Atsiri Kayu Manis *Cinnamomum burmanii* sebagai Bahan Baku Pestisida Nabati untuk Pengendalian Jamur Patogen Tanaman. *Prosiding Seminar dan Kongres XXII Pershimpunan Fitopatologi Indonesia*. 385.
- Pelczar M., J., Chan E., S., C. 2008. *Dasar - Dasar Mikrobiologi 2*. Ratna, S., H., penerjemah: Jakarta: UI Pr. Terjemahan dari: *Elements of Microbiology*. Sirait, M. 2007. *Penuntun Fitokimia dalam Farmasi*. Bandung: ITB.
- Picheansoonthon, C., and Yupparach, P. 2007. Notes on The Genus *Elettariopsis* Baker (Zingiberaceae) in Thailand. *Journal of Thai Traditional & Alternative Medicine*. 5(3): 29–40.
- Ramadhani, P., Mukhtar, H., Prahmono, D. 2018. Uji Aktivitas Antibakteri Ekstrak Etanol Daun Katuk (*Sauropus androgynus* (L.) Merr) terhadap Bakteri *Staphylococcus aureus* dan *Escherichia coli* dengan Metode Difusi Agar. *Indonesia Natural Research Pharmaceutical Journal*. 2(2): 2502 – 8421.
- Sangeetha, J., and Asokan, S. 2015. Antibacterial Activity of Different Sea Grass Extracts Against some Human Eye Pathogens. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 4(12): 677-683.
- Septiani, Dewi, E., N., and Wijayanti, I. 2017. Aktivitas Antibakteri Ekstrak Lamun (*Cymodocea rotundata*) terhadap Bakteri *Staphylococcus aureus* Dan *Escherichia coli*. *Indonesian Journal of Fisheries Science and Technology*. 13(1): 1858-4748.
- Subaryanti, Meianti, D., S., D., and Manalu, R., T. 2022. Potensi Antimikroba Ekstrak Etanol Daun Gatal (*Urticastrum decumanum* Roxb. Kuntze) Terhadap Pertumbuhan *Staphylococcus aureus* dan *Candida albicans*. *Sainstech Farma*. 15(2):2086-7816.
- Syamsuardi, Mansyurdin, Nurainas, and Susanti, T. 2010. Variasi Morfologi Polen Genus *Globba* (Zingiberaceae) di Sumatera Barat. Berk. Penel. Hayati. 16: 89–94.**